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EMM RESEARCH HUB AUSTRIA CODEBUCH UND TEMPLATE

Begleitmaterial zur *EMM Research Hub Datenbank*

EMM AUSTRIA METADATEN TEMPLATE UND CODEPLAN

This document serves as accompanying material for the dataset of the *EMM Research Hub*. The manual is intended to provide orientation within the dataset and to assist in further processing as well as in future additions and extensions of the data. The dataset contains data on social science studies in Austria that deal with migrant minorities in Austria. It includes projects with a wide range of methodological approaches that were initiated between 2003 and 2022.

The following chapters explain the framework conditions for the dataset and present the underlying structure and logic of the data.

The document is structured into the following sections:

1. Clarification about the data/studies included in the dataset
2. Structure of the dataset and explanation of the variables

1. Data and Data Collection Process

The data in the *EMM Research Hub database* include projects and studies that collected primary data on asylum or migration. Both quantitative, qualitative, and mixed-method projects are taken into account. The dataset is based on comprehensive online research across all relevant Austrian research institutions, research documentation, and other institutions and organizations that conduct social science research in the field of migration. As part of a systematic cleaning process, all projects were identified that collected primary data in the form of interviews (group or individual) or surveys. Only these projects are included in the dataset. Detailed information on the selection and recording of the data is documented in the corresponding project report. The database is continuously being expanded, and the time frame of the included projects is being gradually extended.

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Prandner, D., Kern, J. (2025). Codebook and Template for EMM Research Hub Austria Data. Is licensed under a <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

2. Structure of Metadata and Codeplan¹

The structure of the dataset is based on the international *EMM Survey Registry*, which was developed to record and document quantitative data on migrant or ethnic minorities. The data structure includes information about the studies, the associated data material, and the context in which they were created. For the *EMM Research Hub dataset*, the structure was expanded and adapted to also integrate non-quantitative studies and thus enable a broader and more heterogeneous collection of research projects. Wherever possible, the original structure was maintained by incorporating variables and codings from the *EMM Survey Registry*. These were supplemented or refined as needed to build a flexible framework capable of supporting diverse research designs.

Projects are entered into the data collection based on a dataset-based logic. This means that each entry (case) in the data collection reflects a single data collection within a project. This allows multiple datasets — and consequently also individual cases — in the database to be assigned to a single research project. When working with the dataset, this consideration is essential, and applying appropriate weights may be required for accurate analysis.

The database is divided into thematic sections. These eleven sections initially contain information for project identification. They are followed by areas that describe the projects in terms of content and methodology and provide insights into the research approach (e.g., topic focus, research design, sampling process). The concluding sections offer supplementary information on the classification of the projects, the underlying structures, as well as the data sources and the coding process. Each thematic section captures specific aspects of the research projects. Within some sections, there are further subdivisions or recurring elements to represent, for example, multiple sampling procedures within a single project. At the lowest level, specific variables provide comparable data and enable consistent analysis across projects.

The sections and subsections are described below, with all variables and codings listed. In this version of the dataset prepared for public access on the AUSSDA database, some variables had to be removed due to data protection regulations. Additionally, other variables were deleted for clarity and because they were primarily used for internal purposes. A list of the removed variables can be found at the beginning of each section.

¹ This document is based on the publication of Morales, L., Méndez Lago, M., Bernat, A., & Bergh, J. (2021). SURVEYS METADATA TEMPLATE GUIDELINES DOCUMENT: Gathering information on migrant and ethnic minorities surveys (12 May 2021). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4751604>. The descriptions of the overlapping variables have been taken verbatim. In accordance with the CC BY 4.0 license, these contents have been incorporated. They are to be understood as quotations and do not represent original work by the authors of this document.

2.1. Section 1: General Identification Information

This section contains basic information for the identification and classification of datasets and projects. It includes identification variables such as project name, ID, and brief project descriptions, as well as details on study design and a thematic categorization of the collected content.

The structure makes it possible to specifically identify individual projects or datasets and to analyze studies in detail. The included variables provide an overview of the social science research landscape on migration and asylum in Austria and allow for tracking developments in thematic focuses and methodological approaches over time.

Variables deleted:

1.0 Internal project number

1.1a ID Internal

1. General identification information about the study ²		
Variables	Response categories	Comments
1.0. Country	<i>(Open-ended)</i>	Fill in the Countries name or select the appropriate ISO codes. Regarding this dataset, you should mainly refer to Austria.
1.0 Internal project number		This project number refers to the Excel Document <i>EMM_Austria_Projektliste</i> and can be used to match the studies. For additional entries leave open.
1.1a ID Internal	<i>Axxxxa</i>	Use following logic: Uppercase letter (A for quantitative, B for qualitative data), three-digit number (running number starting with 001), one-digit number (indicating wave), lowercase letter (indicating subparts of projects).
1.2. Study acronym	<i>(Open-ended)</i> <i>-9 Don't know</i> <i>-99 Information not available</i> <i>-999 Not applicable</i>	If any used by data producers, only; do not make up one
1.3. Full name of the study - in English	<i>(Open-ended)</i>	
1.4. Full name of the study - in national language(s)	<i>(Open-ended)</i>	
1.5a Based on secondary data	<i>1 Yes</i> <i>0 No</i> <i>-9 Don't know</i> <i>-99 Information not available</i>	If secondary data is used for this project, then mark yes. This concerns project using already existing data for their analysis as their main or additional database. Concerning the accessible version of the dataset, this variable should always be coded as 0
1__ Quant/Qual	<i>1 quantitative study</i> <i>2 qualitative study</i> <i>-9 Don't know</i> <i>-99 Information not available</i>	
1.5. Territorial scope of the study	<i>1 National</i> <i>2 Sub-national</i> <i>3 Transnational</i> <i>-9 Don't know</i>	This variable refers to the territorial level at which the study is designed to be representative.
1.6. If subnational, which level?	<i>1 federal state</i> <i>2 region (district, canon etc.)</i> <i>3 city or town</i> <i>4 multiple federal states</i> <i>5 multiple cities or towns</i>	

² If information is not available or cannot be entered into the file for other reasons, the missing value codes 9/-9 'Don't know', 99/-99 'Information not available', and 999/-999 'Not applicable' are used. The code 'Not applicable' is applied when the variable is not relevant due to the project logic.

	<p>8 other</p> <p>9 Don't know</p> <p>- 99 Information not available -</p> <p>- 999 Not applicable</p>	
1.6b. If transnational, which level?	<p>1 bilateral (EU/Europe)</p> <p>2 multilateral (EU/Europe)</p> <p>3 bilateral (intercontinental)</p> <p>4 multilateral (intercontinental)</p> <p>- 9 don't know</p> <p>- 99 Information not available -</p> <p>- 999 not applicable</p>	
1.7. If subnational, name of region(s) /city(s) covered by study - in English	(Open-ended)	Add all the cities/regions separated by a semi-colon (e.g., Barcelona province; Madrid province)
1.7b. If transnational, name of countries		Fill in if the data collection takes place in several countries. Add all the countries separated by a semi-colon (e.g., Austria; Germany; Netherlands)
1.8. If subnational, name of region(s) /city(s) covered by study - in national language(s)	(Open-ended)	
1.8a. If subnational, add the NUTS/LAU code of the specific cities/regions	(Open-ended)	Add all the NUTS (for regions/provinces) or LAU (for municipalities) codes for the cities/regions separated by a semi-colon (e.g., for Barcelona and Madrid in the example above this would be "ES511; ES300) Please note that this could be the LAU code if the territorial level is a local authority /municipality. The files with the LAU codes can be obtained from Eurostat here: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/nuts/local-administrativeunits
1.8b If subnational, type of subnational area	<p>1 Predominantly urban / Cities (densely populated areas)</p> <p>2 Intermediate / Towns and suburbs (intermediate densely populated areas)</p> <p>3 Predominantly rural (thinly populated areas)</p> <p>4 Mix (more than one subnational area type)</p> <p>-9 Don't know</p> <p>-99 Information not available</p> <p>-999 Not applicable</p>	
1.9. Is the study designed to be "representative" of the (sub)population in this territory?	<p>1 Yes</p> <p>0 No</p> <p>-9 Don't know</p>	The 'representativeness' of a study is always tricky to ascertain, but here we are asking you to ascertain whether broadly speaking the sample design is such that the study will reasonably represent the target population, and/or it claims to be representative of such target population.
1.10_Con. Overall concept of the project	(Open-ended)	Describe the overall concept of the project in one sentence.
1.10x. What method of data collection was used for this study?	<p>_1 Individual interviews</p> <p>_2 Groupinterviews</p> <p>_3 Survey</p> <p>_4 Structural data or register data</p> <p>_5 Content analysis</p> <p>_6 Experiment</p> <p>_7 Observation</p> <p>_8 Other</p> <p>1 Yes</p> <p>0 No</p> <p>- 9 Don't know</p>	Several options can be chosen if a method mix was used. Code each method if used with 1, if not used with 0.
1.10xa.If other in 1.10x specify	(Open-ended)	
1.10. Is it a single cross-section study or a repeated/longitudinal study?	<p>1 Single cross-section</p> <p>2 Repeated cross-section (multiple waves with different samples)</p> <p>3 Longitudinal/panel study (multiple waves with the same or partially overlapping samples)</p> <p>4. Other (mixed design, please specify)</p> <p>-9 Don't know</p>	Here we are only asking about this specific study for the given location (i.e., city/region/country) where it is conducted; multi-site studies can be identified in section 2 below
1.10a. If other in 1.10, specify	(Open-ended)	

1.11. Starting date of the study fieldwork	yyyy -99 <i>Information not available</i>	For repeated or longitudinal studies, here you should report only the fieldwork dates of the wave that this register corresponds to.
1.12. End date of the study fieldwork	yyyy -99 <i>Information not available</i>	For repeated or longitudinal studies, here you should report only the fieldwork dates of the wave that this register corresponds to.
1.11p. Starting date of project	yyyy -9 <i>Don't know</i> -99 <i>Information not available</i>	Fill in the dates for which the project was approved or funded.
1.12p. End date of project	yyyy -9 <i>Don't know</i> -99 <i>Information not available</i>	Fill in the dates for which the project was approved or funded.
1.12a Study is still in development/not yet completed	0 <i>already completed</i> 1 <i>not yet completed</i>	Referring to the point of time the entry was made.
1.13. Main topic(s) covered by the study.	- _1 Asylum seekers and refugee issues - _2 Citizenship and naturalization - _3 Consumption and/or leisure - _4 Demographic characteristics/behaviours - _5 Discrimination, racism and/or xenophobia - _6 Educational attainment/trajectory, human capital, skills - _7 Family reunification, marriage, family relations - _8 Gender relations, gender identity, sexuality - _9 Housing/housing access - _10 Health/health access - _11 Human smuggling and trafficking - _12 Identity (ethnic, national, racial, religious) and belonging - _13 Income-related (and/or poverty) - _14 Interethnic contact and conflict - _15 Labour market integration - _16 Language skills/training - _17 Leisure, sports, arts - _18 Legal status/administrative situation - _19 Migration trajectory (past/future) - _20 Political inclusion and participation, and social/political attitudes - _21 Public attitudes about migration and migrants - _22 Reasons for migration/migration drivers - _23 Return migration - _24 Social cohesion and/or civic engagement and/or networks - _25 Space use/spatial consequences - _26 Time use - _27 Transnational patterns (e.g., remittances, travel, engagement with 'home' country politics, etc.) and diasporas - _28 Unaccompanied migrant minors - _29 Religion - _30 Other	By 'main topics' we refer to topics that are given "considerable" space in the questionnaire. Of course, this will be relative to the length of the questionnaire, but typically we are referring to a set of at least 3-4 questions covering that topic. In other words, a topic is given some attention in the questionnaires and not just 1 or 2 short questions as generic 'control' variables. This variable is set up as a multi-response, such that several of these options can be marked. Please select the option 'Don't know' if you are unsure if a main topic is covered by the study. National teams can only ascertain the topic(s) if they get hold of the questionnaire used.
1.13a. If other in 1.13, specify	(<i>Open-ended</i>)	
1.14. Main purpose of the study.	- _1 Research/academic - _2 Public policy - _3 Government statistics - _4 NGO/non-profit organisation - _5 Commercial - _6 Other	This variable is set up as a multi-response, such that several of these options can be marked. Please select the option 'Don't know' if you are unsure of the main purpose of the study,
1.14a. If other in 1.14, specify	(<i>Open-ended</i>)	
1.15. What is the coverage of the target population in terms of age?	1 <i>Children (up to 12 years-old) only</i> 2 <i>Youth (between 13 – 25 years-old) only</i> 3 <i>Children and youth only</i> 4 <i>Adult population (18+ or 15+) only</i> 5 <i>Elder population only (55+)</i> 6 <i>A combination of minors and adults</i> -9 <i>Don't know</i> -99 <i>Information not available</i>	

1.16. What is the coverage of the target population in terms of the sex of the respondents?	<i>1 Men only</i> <i>2 Women only</i> <i>3 Both men and women</i> <i>-9. Don't know</i> <i>-99 Information not available</i>	
1.17. Comments relevant to variables in section 1	<i>(Open-ended)</i>	Use this section to add any relevant comments relating to variables in section 1. Such fields will be provided in every section.

2.2. Section 2: Inclusion in Larger Study

This section contains information about overarching projects, related studies, and cases. If a project has been entered into the dataset as a subproject of a larger project, the main project is briefly described here along with key data. If multiple data collections were conducted as part of a study, the corresponding links are noted in Section 2. Additionally, all other projects that are connected to the respective data collection (case) can be identified here — including those that relied on secondary data. Section 2 thus primarily serves to locate and assign the data appropriately.

2. Information about the inclusion of the project in a larger study		
Variables	Response categories	Comments
2.2. Study acronym	<i>(Open-ended)</i> -9 Don't know -99 Information not available -999 Not applicable	If any used by data producers, only; do not make up one
2.3. Name of the international/larger programme this study is part of - in English	<i>(Open-ended)</i> -999 Not applicable	
2.4. Name of the international/larger programme this study is part of - in national language(s)	<i>(Open-ended)</i> -999 Not applicable	
2.5. Name of other country(s)/region(s)/city(s) included in the international/larger programme - in English.	<i>(Open-ended)</i>	
2.6. In case of repeated/longitudinal studies: Date of first study in the repeated/longitudinal series	yyyy -99 Information is not available	
2.7. In case of repeated/longitudinal studies: Frequency of waves/panels	<i>(Open-ended)</i> -99 Information not available	Here we want to know how often (approx.) each wave is undertaken (e.g. yearly, every two years, irregular but every 3-5 years, etc.)
2.8. In case of repeated/longitudinal studies: Which wave number corresponds to this study register?	<i>(Number)</i> -99 Information is not available	Here you should specify if the study for which you're coding this particular register is for wave 1, wave 2, etc.
2.9. In the case of studies that are part of an international survey programme: Date from which the study started to be part of an international survey programme for the first time	yyyy -99 Information is not available	
2.10. In the case of studies that are part of an international survey programme: Frequency of waves since then	<i>(Open-ended)</i> -99 Information is not available	Here we want to know how often (approx.) each wave is undertaken (e.g. yearly, every two years, irregular but every 3-5 years, etc.)
2.11. If sample is pooled: how many studies pooled.	<i>(Open-ended)</i>	Pooled samples should be described separately in individual registers. This concerns independently sampled data collected in different location which is then pooled into one dataset.
2.12. If sample is pooled: which other studies pooled.	<i>(Open-ended)</i>	If pooled, fill in the according studies/samples acronyms here. Pooled samples should be described separately in individual registers. This concerns independently sampled data collected in different location which is then pooled into one dataset.
2.12a. If sample is pooled, does the sample include emigrants from more than one country	0 No 1 Yes - 9 Don't know - 99 Information not available - 999 Not applicable	
2.13. Any other qualitative or quantitative studies linked to the survey?	0 No 1 Yes - 9 Don't know - 99 Information not available - 999 Not applicable	Were there any qualitative or quantitative studies done in connection with the study or other data linked to this data?

2.13a Name or Casenumber of study		If an internal ID was assigned, list IDs, otherwise list the name(s) of the study/studies
2.13b If secondary data was used: Name or Casenumber of secondary data		If an internal ID was assigned, list IDs, otherwise list the name(s) of the study/studies
2.14. If yes, please describe these studies	<i>(Open-ended)</i>	Add here all relevant information about the linked studies
2.15. Comments relevant to variables in section 2	<i>(Open-ended)</i>	

2.3. Section 3: Target Population

Section 3 contains information about the studied group: how the target population was defined and operationalized, as well as which key data regarding the migrant background of the respondents were collected in the respective study.

Analyses of this section can provide insights into which groups are the focus of research interest, which ethnic or migrant subgroups are considered particularly relevant for Austrian social research, and for which groups the most information is therefore available.

3. Ethnic and migrant minority target population		
Variables	Response categories	Comments
3.1. EMM Target population: which minority group(s)	<i>(Open-ended)</i>	Please list here the best terms that describe the minority groups covered. This could be "immigrants" or "Roma minority" or "non-EU third country nationals", etc. Even if a 'majority' population sub-group is included, here we are only interested in the description of the EMM groups targeted. If you do not know how to complete this section or you do not have the information to fill in this section, please write this down.
3.1a. EMM target population with terms standardized		Use overall definition (e.g. Migrant, Asylum seeker etc.) and ethnical background or country of origin (e.g. Afghanistan).
3.2. Was the EMM target population....	<i>1 All foreign residents in the city/region/country</i> <i>2. All residents of foreign origin in the city/region/country</i> <i>3 All residents who are 1st or 2nd generation migrants in the city/region/country</i> <i>4 All residents of ethnic minority identification in the city/region/country</i> <i>5 A selection of residents of foreign/migrant origin or ancestry in the city/region/country</i> <i>6 A selection of residents of ethnic minority identification in the city/region/country</i> <i>7 Other (e.g., returning emigrants)</i> <i>-9 Don't know</i> <i>-99 Information not available</i>	Only one should apply.
3.2a. If "Other" in 3.2, describe which	<i>(Open-ended)</i>	

3.3. How is target population defined / operationalized / identified	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - _1 Country of birth of respondent - _2 Country of birth of parents/grandparents - _3 Citizenship/nationality of respondent (current) - _4 Citizenship/nationality of respondent (at birth) - _5 Citizenship/nationality of parents/grandparents (current) - _6 Citizenship/nationality of parents/grandparents (at birth) - _7 Ethnic self-identification of respondent (one response allowed) - _8 Ethnic self-identification of respondent (multiple responses allowed) - _9 Ethnic self-identification of parents/grandparents - _10 Mother tongue/language related question - _11 Classification by interviewer (i.e., the interviewer assigns a subjective value about ethnicity/minority group adscription) - _12 Classification by third agent/proxy (e.g., by a government authority, an NGO, a social/cultural mediator, etc.) - _13 Classification by geographical location - _14 Through other means/characteristics (including non-ethnic/migrant minority-related characteristics) - _15 Information not available on definition of target population 	<p>Multiple responses possible. Mark the criterion-criteria used to define minority group(s). If you do not know if a criterion applies, select 'Don't Know'.</p> <p>Oftentimes, the definition of the target population is not offered in the questionnaire as such, but in additional technical documentation, or in core publications relating to the study. If you have access to them, please check them to see if you find a definition / operationalization of the target population.</p> <p>By citizenship/nationality we mean the actual nationality rights (e.g., to a passport).</p>
3.3a. If "Other means" in 3.3., describe which	<i>(Open-ended)</i>	
3.4. Migrant / minority related questions in the questionnaire	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - _1 Country of birth of respondent - _2 Country of birth of parents - _3 Country of birth of grandparents - _4 Nationality of respondent (current) - _5 Nationality of respondent (at birth) - _6 Nationality of parents (current) - _7 Nationality of grandparents (current) - _8 Nationality of parents (at birth) - _9 Nationality of grandparents (at birth) - _10 Ethnic self- identification of respondent (one response allowed) - _11 Ethnic self- identification of respondent (multiple responses allowed) - _12 Ethnic self-identification of parents - _14 Ethnic self- identification of grandparents - _15 Mother tongue/language related question - _16 Classification by interviewer (i.e., the interviewer assigns a subjective value about ethnicity/minority group adscription) - _17 Information not available on migrant / minority related questions 	<p>Important: this question needs to be answered always, regardless of what you have answered in 3.3. above. Multiple responses possible. In cases when you do not know if a criterion applies, please select 'Don't know'.</p> <p>When designing a study, the researchers might have a core set of variables in mind to identify the target EMM population but can nevertheless add other relevant variables relating to migrant/minority status. Even if they are not used to define the target groups, please report whether the study includes each question in the list.</p> <p>It may be sometimes that these questions are implicitly or explicitly included as part of the screening section of the questionnaire or as part of a general introduction to the study where the respondent can say (s)he does not fit the profile searched. In those cases, mark as if these questions were included.</p>
3.5. Size of the EMM target population/s in the country/region/city as a whole (if available)	<i>(Open-ended)</i> -99 <i>Information not available</i>	Here we would like to get the information about the size of the population(s) on which the sample is likely to have been drawn. Typically, you would know this from either census information or local population registers, which are used as the sampling frame. If this is not available because the sample frame does not provide a count of the underlying

		population (e.g., the sample is addresses instead of individuals), write '-99' for information not available.
3.6. Does the study include a subgroup of majority/autochthonous/general population?	1 Yes 0 No -9 Don't know	
3.6a Study designed as a general population study	1 Yes 0 No -9 Don't know -99 Information not available	Was the study program not aimed specifically at EMMs, but a general population study, which included inter alia data on ethnic minorities or migrants.
3.7. Comments relevant to variables in section 3:	(Open-ended)	

2.4. Section 4: Sampling Method

Section 4 contains information on the sampling method. This allows for an assessment of the structure and quality of the data, as well as its interpretability and usability. Additionally, it reveals which approaches to accessing the research field in Austria have been chosen or are possible.

4. Sampling method		
Variables	Response categories	Comments
4.1. Sampling strategy - closed	<p>1 random sampling/selection (i.e., probability sampling, of some kind)</p> <p>2 non-probability sampling (including snowball/network and purposive samplings)</p> <p>3 mixed sampling procedures (in which there are elements of probability sampling, such as centrelocation sampling)</p> <p>-9. Don't know</p> <p>-99. Information not available</p>	Please choose which category describes best the sampling strategy. Please see Section 3.2 below on annotations relating to specific variables.
4.2. Sampling strategy – open-ended	<p>(Open-ended)</p> <p>-9 Don't know</p> <p>-99 Information not available</p>	<p>Important: this question needs to be answered even if you have already answered 4.1. Add specifics that allow to understand better your answer in 4.1. If the answer is unknown, please enter in '-9'. If the information is not available, please enter in - 99.</p> <p>Sample design strategy: for example, stratified random sample (and describe which strata and if oversample or proportional to population size), quota sampling, random route sampling, etc.</p> <p>Describe specific sample design technique: (open-ended field to describe with some detail). Please see Section 3.2 below on annotations relating to specific variables.</p>
4.3. Sample design – full additional information	<p>(Open-ended)</p>	Please add all the essential information for a reader to understand how the sample was designed without referring to the study documentation.
4.4. Sampling frame(s)	<p>(Open-ended)</p> <p>-9 Don't know</p> <p>-99 Information not available</p>	<p>This is the list, census of the population or addresses, or rolling population register/list of households from which sample extracted.</p> <p>Please also add the name of the list as such in the original country language for precise identification.</p>
4.5. Sampling units	<p>(Open-ended)</p> <p>-9 Don't know</p> <p>-99 Information not available</p>	<p>Individuals? Families? Households? Addresses? Census sections? etc.</p> <p>Please provide information on ALL sampling units used in the design (primary, secondary, etc.)</p>
4.6. Comments and additional information on the sampling method	<p>(Open-ended)</p>	<p>Use this section to expand on any relevant details about sampling, especially if the documentation is partial and you can only provide information about effective population covered.</p> <p>Please see Section 3.2 below on annotations relating to specific variables.</p>

2.5. Section 5: Sample Size

Section 5 contains information on the sample. Primarily, sample sizes are reported here.

5. Sample size for the overall study		
Variables	Response categories	Comments
5.1. Total gross/issued sample	(Number) -9 Don't Know -99 Information not available	Here we are interested in the full sample for this particular study (wave). If this is a general population study, you should include the overall sample size for all respondents. If this is a study broken down by subsamples to specific groups, we want here the overall number of respondents targeted across all groups.
5.2. Total net/achieved sample	(Number) - 9 Don't know - 99 Information not available	As above
5.3. Overall response rate	(Number) -9 Don't know -99 Information not available	Please provide the response rate reported by the data producers in the first instance (see Section 3.1 below on annotations relating to specific variables)
5.4. How was overall response rate calculated	1 By data producers with no mentioned formula; 2 AAPOR; 3 AAPOR RR1; 4 ESS; 5 Other -9 Don't Know -99 Information not available	
5.5. If response rate calculated as "5=Other", please describe	(Open-ended)	Give as many details as possible about how response rates were calculated
5.6. Comments about any known issues with the sample and representativeness or biases	(Open-ended)	Fill in only if available in documentation or existing research relating to this study. We do not expect you to run your own analysis about the quality of the sample
5.7. Are any weights provided?	1 Yes 0 No -9 Don't Know -99 Information not available	
5.8. If there are any weights, please describe	(Open-ended)	
5.9. Comments relevant to variables in section 5	(Open-ended)	

2.6. Section 6: Sample Size for Subgroups

Section 6 contains sample information on subgroups. This section is only relevant for projects in which specific data on certain ethnic or migrant groups were collected as part of larger surveys.

6. Sample sizes for any subgroups in which the study is partitioned		
Variables	Response categories	Comments
Subgroup #1 (= SG1)	<p>We will provide at least 5 repetitions of this battery of questions for up to 5 subgroups in which the study is partitioned (6a to 6e).</p> <p>These variables only need to be filled in if the sample was partitioned by groups (e.g., 3-4 nationalities for migrant groups; 2-3 ethnic minorities; migrants vs majority population; etc.).</p> <p>Important: if a study is designed as a multi-city one but the samples are designed separately for each city (e.g., from different sample frames for each city), a separate record should be created for each city.</p> <p>Please sort by the achieved sample size.</p>	
6a1. SG1 name of sub-group	(Open-ended)	<p>Write here the name of this subgroup as defined in the study documentation.</p> <p>For example: "Turkish migrants", "Autochthonous population", "Refugees".</p>
6a2. SG1 gross/issued sample	(number) - 99 = Information not available	
6a3. SG1 net/achieved sample	(number) - 99 = Information not available	
6a4. SG1 response rate	(number) - 99 = Information not available	Please provide the response rate reported by the data producers in the first instance
6a5. SG1 How was overall response rate calculated	<p>1. by data producers with no mentioned formula;</p> <p>2. AAPOR;</p> <p>3 AAPOR RR1;</p> <p>4 ESS;</p> <p>5 Other</p> <p>-9 Don't Know</p> <p>-99 Information not available</p>	
6a6. SG1 If response rate calculated as "5=Other", please describe	(Open-ended)	Give as many details as possible about how response rates were calculated
6a7. SG1 Comments about any known issues with the sample and representativeness or biases	(Open-ended)	Fill in only if available in documentation or existing research relating to this study. We do not expect you to run your own analysis about the quality of the sample
6.8 Comments relevant to variables in section 6		

2.7. Section 7: Data Collection Information

Section 7 Contains specific information on the data collection methods, including the form of data collection as well as details about interviewers and language skills. This section is divided into subsections a to e, which can be used if multiple different data collection methods were employed in the project.

Analyses of this section provide insights into the structure of the data and the potentially specific requirements involved in data collection on migrant or ethnic minorities.

Variables deleted:

7.1. Name of person/institution/institute that undertook fieldwork

7. Data collection information		
Variables	Response categories	Comments
Method 1	<p>We will provide at least 5 repetitions of this battery of questions for up to 5 different types of data generated in the study (7a to 7e).</p> <p>These variables only need to be filled in if a method mix was used and the data cannot be separated or the additional data cannot be used on their own. Otherwise please enter data as individual cases.</p>	
7.1. Name of person/institution/institute that undertook fieldwork	<i>(Open-ended)</i> - 99 = Information not available	Please add here the full name of the institution(s) or research institute(s) that carried out the fieldwork. This might be a university where the fieldwork was organised in-house, or a professional survey company, or a single individual (e.g., for studies done in the context of PhD dissertations)
7.2. Data collection mode	_ 1 Face to face (PAPI); _ 2 Face to face (CAPI); _ 3 Telephone; _ 4 Web/email study; _ 5 Paper self- administered (collected) _ 6 Paper self- administered (postal) _ 7 Other 99 Information not available on data collection mode	Multiple options possible. If the study is mixed-mode, select 1 'Yes' for all that apply. If you are unsure if a collection mode was used or not, select 'Don't know'. If you do not have any information on the data collection mode(s), code 99 for 'Information not available'.
7.2.8 If "Other" in 7.2., describe which	<i>(Open-ended)</i>	
7.3. For personal interviews: who interviewed?	1 Professional interviewers only 2 Cultural mediator only 3 Non-professional interviewers (e.g., students) 4 A mix -9 Don't know -99 Information not available	
7.4. For personal interviews: interviewers spoke migrant or ethnic minority group languages?	1 Yes 2 No, but translator(s) present/available 3 No, nobody had targeted language skills -9 Don't Know -99 Information not available	
7.5. If yes, which?	<i>(Open-ended)</i>	For later coding into international standard codes for languages (ISO)
7.6. Questionnaire available in languages of migrants or ethnic minorities other than official languages?	1 Yes 0 No -9 Don't know -99 Information not available	
7.7. If yes, which?	<i>(Open-ended)</i>	For later coding into international standard codes for languages (ISO)

7.8. Average duration/length of interview	<i>(In minutes)</i> -9 = <i>Don't know</i> -99 = <i>Information not available</i>	
7.9. Number of questions in the questionnaire	<i>(Number)</i> -9 = <i>Don't know</i> -99 = <i>Information not available</i>	<p>By 'questions', we mean the number of 'question items' (i.e., every time the respondent needs to provide an answer to something). Thus, a question that asks for the opinion on (e.g.) 4 different institutions counts for 4.</p> <p>If you have access to the dataset, oftentimes the quickest way to establish the number of question items is to open the dataset with your statistical software of choice and query the software for the total number of variables in the dataset.</p> <p>If you are unable to tell what the number of questions is (e.g., for CAPI surveys, or dataset not available) and cannot even give a sensible approximation, please code as -9. If you do not have access to the information needed to respond to this question, please enter -99.</p>
7.10. Comments relevant to variables in section	<i>(Open-ended)</i>	Please add any further comment on data collection that could be relevant to users
QQual7_1. If qualitative, please describe the method of analysis	<i>(Open-ended)</i> -9 <i>Don't know</i> -99 <i>Information not available</i> -999 <i>not applicable</i>	If the data is based on qualitative methods of data collection, please briefly describe the method of analysis, if available.

2.8. Section 8: Availability

Section 8 Provides information on the availability of and access to data and other materials. If available, this section also includes links to data archives or other data documentation platforms.

Anyone wishing to use data from the projects or obtain more detailed information about studies or results will find potential access options here.

8. Availability		
Variables	Response categories	Comments
8.1. Availability of the study data matrix (the dataset with the individual responses) for individual research use	<i>1 Yes, publicly available</i> <i>2 Available through a COST Action member</i> <i>3 Available by request</i> <i>4 Unavailable</i> <i>5 Unknown availability</i>	
8.2. If publicly available or by request, where is the study dataset stored	<i>(Open-ended)</i>	If in a repository, please provide a URL for the respective data catalogue page, otherwise, describe as text who to contact
8.3. Identification number of the archive/repository where the dataset is stored	<i>(Open-ended)</i>	If data are already in a repository, please provide the identification number or code with which the dataset can be found in the archive. If no identification number is available, and a name is provided instead, please add the name.
8.4. DOI for the dataset	<i>(DOI format)</i>	If available, write in DOI format
8.5. Access to complete dataset	<i>1 Yes, micro-data available for download/direct access by researchers</i> <i>2 Yes, but micro-data only available for online analyses</i> <i>3 Yes, but micro-data only available to analyse on a secure office/premises of the data archive or data producer</i> <i>4 Yes, but with other restrictions</i> <i>5 No</i> <i>-9 Don't know</i>	Here we want to have the information about how the data can be accessed, if more information is relevant, please add in the Observations field at the end of this section.
8.6. Access to portions of the dataset	<i>1 Yes</i> <i>0 No</i> <i>-9 Don't know</i> <i>-999 Not applicable (full dataset accessible)</i>	Important: In the case of a study which contains sensitive data, these data might be removed from the standard access and only available through a more restricted access, or removed completely; in other cases, researchers might choose to share only part of the dataset due to other confidentiality reasons.
8.7. Access to aggregate data results (e.g., via online databases)	<i>1 Yes</i> <i>0 No</i> <i>-9 Don't know</i>	
8.8. If there are any restrictions for data access in 8.5, 8.6 and 8.7, describe which	<i>(Open-ended)</i>	
8.9. Language(s) in which dataset is available	<i>(Open-ended)</i>	For later coding into international standard codes for languages (ISO)

8.10. Availability of the technical study documentation for individual research use	<i>1 Yes, publicly available</i> <i>2 Available through a COST Action member</i> <i>3 Available by request</i> <i>4 Unavailable</i> <i>Unknown availability</i>	
8.11. If available, where is the technical study documentation stored	<i>(Open-ended)</i>	If in a repository, please provide a URL for the respective data catalogue page, otherwise, describe as text who to contact
8.12. Identification number of the archive/repository where technical documentation is stored		If data already in a repository
8.13. DOI for the documentation	<i>(DOI format)</i>	If available, write in DOI format
8.14. If the technical documentation is available, standard used for the documentation:	<i>1 Data Documentation Initiative</i> <i>2 Dublin Core</i> <i>3 SDMX</i> <i>4 No specific standard</i> <i>-9 Don't know</i>	
8.15. Language(s) in which technical study documentation is available	<i>(Open-ended)</i>	For later coding into international standard codes for languages (ISO)
8.16. Availability of the study questionnaire for individual research use	<i>1 Publicly available</i> <i>2 Available through a COST Action member</i> <i>3 Available by request</i> <i>4 Unavailable</i> <i>5 Unknown availability</i>	
8.17. If available, where is the study questionnaire stored	<i>(Open-ended)</i>	If in a repository, please provide a URL for the respective data catalogue page, otherwise, describe as text who to contact
8.18. Identification number of the archive/repository where questionnaire is stored		If questionnaire already in a repository
8.19. DOI for the questionnaire	<i>(DOI format)</i>	If available
8.20. Language(s) in which study questionnaire is available	<i>(Open-ended)</i>	For later coding into international standard codes for languages (ISO)
8.21. Comments relevant to variables in section 8: on data availability, including any relevant legal/copyright requirements or restrictions for data access	<i>(Open-ended)</i>	<p>Please add any further comment on data availability that could be relevant to users.</p> <p>Important: If the data includes restrictions for further sharing of the dataset such that individual researchers can download/access the data but cannot share it further on, please mention it here.</p>

2.9. Section 9: Data Producers, Owners, Distributors, and Citation

Section 9 provides supplementary information on the research context — including the actors involved (e.g., researchers), the institutional framework, and available contact details.

The variables included in this section can offer insights into the structure of the Austrian research landscape in the field of migration and integration research.

Variables deleted:

- 9.1. Institution/team responsible for data production
- 9.2. Institution/team that owns the data
- 9.3. Institution/team distributing the dataset
- 9.4. Contact details for queries/requests
- 9.5. Citation for dataset
- 9.6. Citation for technical documentation
- 9.7. Citation(s) for any other publications
- 9.8. Comments

9. Data producers, owners, distributors, and citations		
Variables	Response categories	Comments
9.1. Institution/team responsible for data production	<i>(Open-ended)</i>	This is typically the team or institution/study institute that undertook fieldwork
9.1.1 Which academic discipline can the project be assigned to?	<i>501 Psychology</i> <i>502 Economic studies</i> <i>503 Educational studies</i> <i>504 Sociology</i> <i>505 Legal studies</i> <i>506 Political studies</i> <i>507 Human geography, regional geography, regional planning</i> <i>508 Media and communication studies</i> <i>509 other social studies</i> <i>-9 Don't know</i> <i>-99 Not available</i>	If the project lead consists of several team and the study cannot be assigned to a specific discipline enter -999 not applicable. If one main leader team can be identified, please enter the disciplinary background of that team.
9.1.2 How was the research head (team) composed concerning gender	<i>1 all female project leaders</i> <i>2 all, male project leaders</i> <i>3 mixed leader team</i> <i>4 non binary leader team</i> <i>-9 Don't know</i> <i>-99 Not available</i>	
9.1.3 Highest qualification of the research head.	<i>1 research assistant without diploma/masters degree</i> <i>2 Prae doctoral fellow or researcher (master/diplom)</i> <i>3 Post doctoral researcher (Doc/Phd)</i> <i>4 Univ. Professor</i> <i>8 other</i> <i>-9 Don't know</i> <i>-99 Information not available</i>	
9.2. Institution/team that owns the data	<i>(Open-ended)</i>	This is typically the team/institution that paid for the survey and holds copyrights/intellectual property rights. It can be more than one (e.g., if paid by a government unit but led by a research institution), and if so, add here both.

9.2.1. What organisation is the project funded by	1 FWF 2 ÖFG 3 FFG 4 OeNB 5 AWS 8 other - 9 Don't know - 99 Information not available - 999 Not applicable	
9.2.1a. If other, which funding	(Open-ended)	
9.3. Institution/team distributing the dataset	(Open-ended)	The institution/team in charge of sharing the data with future users
9.4. Contact details for queries/requests	(Open-ended)	Who to contact to request access to the data, or for redistribution
9.5. Citation for dataset	(Open-ended)	Add suggested dataset citation here, as a text field. Many repositories or data producers have such a suggestion
9.6. Citation for technical documentation	(Open-ended)	Same as above
9.7. Citation(s) for any other publications	(Open-ended)	Same as above
9.8. Comments	(Open-ended)	

2.10. Section 10: Additional Information

Section 10 contains information on data quality and the informational basis on which this case was coded.

All information from Section 10 was removed from the dataset available through AUSSDA.

10. Additional Information		
Variables	Response categories	Comments
10.1. General subjective assessment of the data quality	From 0 "Extremely poor" to 10 "Extremely good" -9 Don't know	This is a subjective assessment by the COST national teams and is intended as a guideline of whether future efforts of making the data available or pooling it with other datasets are worth the while. It will NOT be made public in this format with the metadata template. It will only be used for internal COST decisionmaking about prioritization of next steps with questionnaires and post-harmonization. Quality should be judged, primarily, on the basis of the availability of the relevant documentation, the transparency of the methods used, and the a priori appropriateness of the methods used. These are typically judgements about the 'input/process' of the study. If the person coding the metadata template has used the dataset, then "output" quality (e.g., quality of the responses, response rates, etc.) can also be used to make this judgement.
10.2. Additional Information about quality of the data	(Open-ended)	Please add here any comment you think is relevant about the data quality
10.3. Sources of information	(Open-ended)	Add here the sources from which you obtained the information you have added in this template.
10.4. Any other comments about the study	(Open-ended)	Add any other comments you think are relevant and are not covered elsewhere

2.11. Section 11: Information on this Compilation of Metadata

Section 11 includes metadata about the data collection process of the database, including the person who entered the respective data record as well as the date of entry. Due to the continuous updating and expansion of the dataset, this is relevant for ensuring the traceability of the composition of the database.

All information from Section 10 was removed from the dataset available through AUSSDA.

11. Information on this compilation of metadata		
Variables	Response categories	Comments
11.1 Person(s) filling in this file		
11.2 Date when this part was last updated	<i>Dd/mm/yyyy</i>	
11.3 Time coverage for the studies included in this file		When additional data is included in the dataset this variable has to be updated.